

Mindfulness and Forgiveness: Insights from Middle Adult Populations

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The present study examines the relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness in middle-aged adults. Participants were assessed based on questionnaires, namely the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale and the Heartland Forgiveness Scale, to analyze the two constructs. Findings revealed that individuals reported moderate levels of both forgiveness and mindfulness. Results further suggested a positive relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness, supporting the hypothesis that higher levels of mindfulness are linked with greater tendencies toward forgiveness. Gender differences were also evaluated however, no significant variations were observed between men and women in relation to either mindfulness or forgiveness, although slight differences emerged in effect size estimates. Overall, the study highlights the meaningful role of mindfulness in fostering forgiveness while indicating that gender does not play a pivotal role in this relationship. This association also highlights the broader framework of positive psychology, where cultivating strengths such as mindfulness and forgiveness contributes to strengthened well-being and personal growth.

Keywords: Forgiveness, mindfulness, middle adulthood, gender differences, positive psychology

Middle adulthood, typically covering ages 40 to 65, is marked by notable physiological, psycho-emotional, and social changes that often bring constraints such as stress, health concerns, and shifting family responsibilities (Lachman, 2004; Santrock, 2021; Papalia, Martorell, & Feldman, 2023). Research highlights that mindfulness, defined as a present-focused, nonjudgmental awareness of one's experiences, is associated with better emotional regulation and reduced rumination (Brown & Ryan, 2003) while forgiveness, understood as letting go of resentment and negative emotions, is linked to enhanced psychological well-being (Worthington & Scherer, 2004). Both constructs are central to positive psychology and have been shown to promote resilience, happiness, and healthier relationships (Webb et al., 2012). Stressors in this stage include occupational pressures, unmet career expectations, financial instability, and role strain, with studies reporting higher levels of job-related stress among middle-aged professionals, particularly in competitive sectors (Bhatia & Sharma, 2023; Zhou, 2023; Lachman et al., 2020). Women in midlife also face unique challenges, including caregiving for both children and ageing parents, relationship changes, and identity reassessment (Mitchell & Woods, 2018). Prolonged stress during this period has further been

associated with cognitive decline, highlighting the importance of stress management and well-being practices (National Institutes of Health, 2014). Overall, mindfulness and forgiveness serve as protective factors that can buffer the adverse effects of stress and foster well-being during this crucial life stage. Middle adulthood often involves a convergence of challenges, including workplace stress, financial strains, shifting family responsibilities, emerging cognitive changes, and health issues, and recognizing these complexities is crucial for developing effective strategies that bolster well-being and resilience during this pivotal life stage (Lachman, 2015). In this context, practices such as mindfulness and forgiveness serve as valuable psychological resources that can buffer stress, enhance coping, and promote healthier adjustment.

Forgiveness is a multifaceted psychological process that involves consciously releasing resentment, negative emotions, and vengeful desires, thereby fostering compassion and empathy toward those who have caused harm (Enright, 2001; Worthington & Scherer, 2004). Rather than being solely moral or religious, forgiveness has important psychological implications, as it is associated with reduced distress and improved well-being (Toussaint, Worthington, & Williams, 2015). Research further indicates that forgiving individuals often report lower levels of depression, anxiety, and anger, reflecting its positive role in emotional health (Toussaint et al., 2018). Similarly, mindfulness, defined as a nonjudgmental awareness of the present moment (Brown & Ryan, 2003), has been widely recognized for its benefits in stress reduction, emotional regulation, and cognitive flexibility (Shapiro et al., 2006). By cultivating acceptance and non-reactivity, mindfulness enables individuals to navigate negative emotions more effectively, which in turn supports a balanced psychological state. Emerging research highlights a strong connection between mindfulness and forgiveness, suggesting that mindful individuals are more likely to adopt forgiving attitudes, as mindfulness reduces emotional reactivity while fostering compassion toward oneself and others (Walsh & Shapiro, 2006).

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Forgiveness and mindfulness are interrelated psychological processes that play a critical role in emotional well-being, particularly during middle adulthood, a period often marked by career transitions, shifting family responsibilities, and personal challenges (Berry et al., 2020; Lachman et al., 2020). Forgiveness, defined as the conscious decision to release resentment and cultivate compassion toward those who have caused harm, has been consistently linked to reduced depression, anxiety, stress, and improved physical and psychological health (Worthington & Scherer, 2004; Worthington et al., 2016; Lawler-Row et al., 2008). Similarly, mindfulness, nonjudgmental awareness of the present moment, enhance emotion regulation, reduces negative affect, and fosters self-compassion (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Shapiro et al., 2006; Neff et al., 2021). Research further highlights that mindfulness facilitates forgiveness by reducing emotional reactivity and encouraging empathy, suggesting that mindful individuals are more likely to adopt forgiving attitudes (Walsh & Shapiro, 2006; Toussaint et al., 2018). Together, mindfulness and forgiveness act as mutually reinforcing processes that support adaptive coping, healthier relationships, and greater psychological resilience in adulthood.

Recent studies highlight the mechanisms underlying this relationship. Neurobiological evidence suggests that mindfulness activates brain regions responsible for emotional regulation, thereby supporting forgiveness processes (Tang et al., 2017). Longitudinal and cross-cultural research further confirms that mindfulness training enhances forgiveness across diverse contexts, improving resilience, social cohesion, and workplace relationships (Lin et al., 2023; O'Brien et al., 2024). Moreover, self-compassion and self-kindness, often cultivated through mindfulness, are strong predictors of forgiveness in adulthood (Neff & Germer, 2019; Kearns & Fincham, 2020). Collectively, findings indicate that mindfulness and forgiveness are mutually reinforcing processes that reduce negative affect, foster positive emotional states, and contribute to psychological well-being and healthy adaptation, particularly during middle adulthood when interpersonal and emotional challenges are heightened that might help an individual to have a better life in their future (Worthington, 2006; Worthington et al., 2001).

In middle adulthood, a developmental phase is often characterized by career pressures, caregiving responsibilities, health concerns, and reflection on past experiences where mindfulness and forgiveness play a vital role in promoting psychological well-being. The ability to practice cognitive flexibility and nonjudgmental acceptance (Bishop et al., 2004; Shapiro et al., 2006) helps adults to cope more effectively with stressors, manage interpersonal conflicts, and maintain emotional stability. Interventions such as Mindfulness-Based Forgiveness Therapy, the REACH Forgiveness Program, and Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (Carson et al., 2005; Worthington et al., 2019; Hayes et al., 2000) are particularly beneficial at this stage, as they help individuals process unresolved traumas, release negative emotions, and cultivate compassion toward themselves and others. Engagement in fostering healthier relationships, reducing anxiety, and enhancing resilience, mindfulness and forgiveness enable adults to navigate life's transitions more positively, contributing to a greater sense of fulfillment and psychological growth during middle adulthood (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Ryff & Singer, 1998; Kabat-Zinn, 2003; Worthington & Scherer, 2004).

Aim of the Study

The aim of this present article is to examine the major relationship

between forgiveness and mindfulness in middle adulthood across the gender.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the level of Forgiveness and Mindfulness among young adults.
- To study the relationship between Forgiveness and Mindfulness among young adults.
- To study the difference in Forgiveness in males and females among young adults.
- To study the difference in Mindfulness in males and females among young adults.

Hypotheses of the Study

- (H1) There will be a significant relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness among middle-aged adults.
- (H2) There will be a significant difference in levels of forgiveness between males and females. (H3) There will be a significant difference in levels of mindfulness between males and females.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 200 participants (46% female & 54% male) aged 40-65 years, representing the selected sample of middle adulthood individuals. Participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique, a non-probability method suitable for selecting individuals who meet predefined inclusion criteria relevant to the research objectives. This sampling approach ensured that all participants belonged to the target age group and could provide meaningful data regarding mindfulness and forgiveness. Demographic information, including age, gender, education, marital status, and occupation, was collected to explore potential differences across subgroups. The participants reflected varied socio-economic status (SES), classified into low, middle, and high categories based on a composite assessment of educational attainment, occupational status, and household income.

Research Design

The present study incorporated a comparative, cross-sectional, quantitative research design to examine the relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness among middle-aged adults (aged 40-65 years). Quantitative data were collected and analyzed statistically to ensure objective, reliable, and valid results. The study assumed that individuals with higher levels of mindfulness tend to exhibit greater tendencies toward forgiveness, which in turn enhances their psychological well-being, self-compassion, and interpersonal relationships.

Measures

Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS): The Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS), developed by Thompson et al. (2005) was employed to measure dispositional forgiveness. It assesses forgiveness across three domains-self, others, and situations-through 18 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *almost always false* to 7 = *almost always true*). Higher scores indicate a greater tendency toward forgiveness. The scale demonstrates strong internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .87$) and satisfactory subscale reliability (ranging from .72 to .83). Its construct and criterion validity are well established through

correlations with emotional regulation and psychological well-being.

Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS): Mindfulness was assessed using the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) developed by Brown and Ryan (2003). The scale comprises 15 items rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = *almost always* to 6 = *almost never*), where higher scores indicate greater mindfulness and present-moment awareness. The MAAS measures a single dimension of mindfulness and demonstrates high internal consistency ($\alpha = .80.90$). Its validity has been confirmed through correlations with emotional intelligence, self-awareness, and life satisfaction.

Procedure

Prior to data collection, ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional review board to ensure participants' rights, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Participants were approached both online (via platforms such as WhatsApp & Google Forms) and offline (through in-person distribution of printed questionnaires).

After obtaining informed consent, participants completed a demographic questionnaire followed by the HFS and MAAS scales. They were instructed to respond honestly, based on their experiences over the past month. Data collection took place over several weeks, ensuring that participants had adequate time to complete the instruments.

Following data collection, responses were coded, cleaned, and entered into a statistical software package for analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics.

- *Descriptive Statistics:* Mean and standard deviation (M ± SD) were computed for mindfulness and forgiveness scores.
- *Inferential Statistics:*
 - Independent Samples t-test was used to examine gender differences in mindfulness and forgiveness.
 - Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation was employed to assess the relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness.
- *Effect Size (Cohen's d):* Effect sizes were calculated to determine the magnitude of gender differences (0.2 = small, 0.5 = medium, 0.8 = large).

Assumptions of Parametric Tests

To ensure statistical validity, the following assumptions were tested:

Normality: The data were assessed for normal distribution.

Homogeneity of Variance: Variance across groups was tested for equality.

Linearity: The relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness was expected to be linear.

Independence of Observations: Each participant's responses were independent.

If assumptions were violated, non-parametric alternatives were planned: Spearman's rank correlation for non-normal data and Welch's t-test for heterogeneity of variance.

Expected Outcomes

It is hypothesized that individuals with higher levels of mindfulness will exhibit greater forgiveness tendencies. Mindful individuals are

expected to display enhanced emotional regulation, self-compassion, and interpersonal harmony, allowing them to manage hurtful experiences more constructively. A positive correlation ($p < .05$) is anticipated between mindfulness and forgiveness, suggesting that mindfulness-based practices can serve as effective interventions to improve emotional resilience and well-being during middle adulthood.

Results

The study aimed at exploring the difference between mindfulness and forgiveness among middle-aged adults. The study was conducted with 200 participants (44% female & 56% male) in the age group 40-65.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics Indicating Means and Standard Deviations of Forgiveness and Mindfulness of Middle Adults

	M	SD
Forgiveness (hfs)	79.20	9.712
Mindfulness (maas)	3.76	.811

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the two variables, i.e., mindfulness and forgiveness. For each variable the table represents the total number of valid responses (N), minimum and maximum score and mean and standard deviation.

- Forgiveness has a mean of 79.20 with a standard deviation of 9.712.
- Mindfulness has a mean of 3.76 with a standard deviation of 0.811.

Table 2

Correlation between Mindfulness and Forgiveness in Middle Adults

	M	SD	F	M
Forgiveness (hfs)	79.20	9.712	1	
Mindfulness (maas)	3.76	.811	.267**	1

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Pearson's Correlation was calculated to SS, the relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness. From the study, the results showed a significant positive correlation, $r = 0.267, p < .001$, which means that individuals with a high level of mindfulness usually tend to report a higher level of forgiveness. This supports previous studies that mindfulness not only helps people to develop their emotions or resolve conflict but also helps an individual to build empathy, self-compassion, understanding towards others and remove past grudges.

People who practice mindfulness attempt to forgive easily (Karremans et al., 2007). Although the strength of the correlation is modest, it has been suggested that practising mindfulness could be beneficial for not only building positive relationships but also enhancing emotional well-being.

Table 3

Indicating Mean Difference in Terms of Forgiveness in Male and Female Middle Adults

Variables	Female	Male	F	Sig.	tM
Forgiveness (hfs)	80.52	10.743	78.61	8.743	7.180 .008 1.381

Figure 1

Indicating the Mean Values of Forgiveness in Male and Female Middle-Aged Adults

Figure 2

Indicating the Mean Values of Mindfulness in Male and Female Middle Adults

Figure 2

Indicating the Mean Values of Mindfulness in Male and Female Middle Adults

Variable	Mean (Male)	SD (Male)	Mean (Female)	SD (Female)	t	p	Cohen's d
Mindfulness (MAAS)	3.89	0.85	3.66	0.77	1.68	.196	1.93

Discussion

The present study intends to find out the relation between mindfulness and forgiveness in middle-aged adult samples. Pearson correlation results show a highly significant positive relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness ($r=.267; p < .001$). As we have seen in the Pearson correlation, the value is $r= 0.267$, which indicates that there is a moderate relationship between the two. It can also be said that if an individual practices mindfulness, forgiveness might increase. But the value which we have received, which is $r= 0.267$, does not have that extreme relationship (Brown & Ryan, 2003). Also, the $p < 0.001$, which is less than 0.1, states that the correlation is statistically significant, meaning that the result occurring by chance is less than 0.1% (Karremans et al., 2004). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted (H1) as it shows no relationship, and we also conclude by saying that there is a positive relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness in middle adulthood.

Therefore, it supports the primary hypothesis of the study. Even in the previous research, it has been seen that in many papers, mindfulness and forgiveness are quite related to each other and highlight the importance of practice, which usually enhances the individual's compassion, and acceptance, and regulates individual emotion. All these traits are often central to the act of forgiveness (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Karremans et al., 2004).

The term mindfulness means a person being aware of the present moment, being open to thoughts and non-judgemental, which allows the people to process hurtful experiences in a less reactive way, which may help people to develop great understanding and forgiveness towards others practicing mindfulness also provide better mental health and encourages individuals to forgive others easily and move forward from the past situation and circumstances (Zeidan et al., 2010). From the objective, we can say that people with a higher level of mindfulness could correlate with a greater level of forgiveness. For example, if people have scored higher in mindfulness, their forgiveness will also be higher (Karremans et al., 2004).

This study's finding suggests that individuals who have a high level of mindfulness may be more inclined to let go of the past, or bitterness towards someone for something they have done and they tend to forgive people easily. They usually not only try to forgive others but also have the potential to forgive themselves. Forgiveness is understood not as a passive act of excusing wrong, but as an active and deliberate choice to reduce all the negative effects and move forward without holding any kind of grudges or negative effects towards others or themselves (Thompson et al., 2005).

The present study also focused on finding the mean difference in terms of forgiveness in males and females in middle adulthood. The result indicates in (Table 3), that there was no statistically significant difference between genders in either mindfulness or forgiveness ($p= .055$), so the hypotheses is rejected (H2) and the mean difference in term of mindfulness in males and females in middle adults present in the result which indicates in (Table 3), that there was no statistically significant difference between genders in either mindfulness or forgiveness ($p= .055$), the hypothesis is rejected (H3). The result indicates in Table 3 that there was no statistically significant difference between genders in either mindfulness or forgiveness ($p= .055$), so the hypothesis is rejected. In the study, we have tried to understand the level of significance, which is denoted by Alpha. It usually represents the Threshold below which we reject the null hypothesis when it is true. The common level of significance is 0.05%, 0.01%, 0.001%. 0.05 represents a standard threshold where we expect a 5% chance of being wrong. The second one is 0.01, which is a slightly strict threshold; it is used when the data is slightly correct and the last one is 0.001 when the data is accurately correct. From the data, we can see that in Females ($N=89$), the mean is 80.52 and the SD is 10.743 and in males ($N=110$); whereas Mean is 78.61 and the SD is 8.743. In the T-test which we have done with the data for this study, over there, p-value (2-tailed) = 0.178 which is greater than 0.05% and the mean difference is 1.908 as the p-value is greater than 0.05%. The difference between males and females is not that statically significant from the studies, we can see that females are

slightly higher than the male. This total score was for Forgiveness (totals).

From the data, we can see that in the Female ($N=89$); where the Mean is 3.8869 and, in the male ($N=110$); where the Mean is 3.6648. In the t-test which we have done with the data for this study, over there, p -value (2-tailed) = 0.055, which is greater than 0.05% and the mean difference is 0.22204, as the p -value is greater than 0.05%. The difference between them is not statistically significant from the studies; we can see that females are slightly higher in mindfulness than males. This total code was for Mindfulness (total mass).

Although the difference in the mindfulness approach is significant. This shows that there is no significance between males and females and have relatively similar levels of mindfulness and forgiveness. From the data, we can see that 54% was male and 46% was female. From this, we can say that a slight difference between the gender size (Cohen's $d = .197$ for forgiveness; $d = 0.218$ for mindfulness) was seen. It is not statistically significant (Rojiani et al., 2017). If the same study was done on a large population, then there might be a gender difference. In the future, if the same research is done on a large sample and the varieties of culture, then there might be gender differences, which might help us understand the relationship between forgiveness and mindfulness.

Previous literature has not been so consistent regarding gender differences in these variables. According to many researchers, it has been seen that some have said that males may engage in high levels of forgiveness due to being practical, realistic, and logical and because of moral reasons, which may not always be correct (Miller et al., 2008). In contrast to other research, researchers have said that women tend to report higher levels of forgiveness as they are caring and provide support and encouragement. Apart from caring and support, they also provide emotional and intellectual nurturing, which helps the individual to feel like a part of society. However, these findings are heavily influenced by many other factors such as character differences, rules and regulations of a particular culture, which might explain why a significant difference was not found in the study (Rojiani et al., 2017).

From a psychological point of view, both mindfulness and forgiveness are important to reduce individual burden and conflict. They also provide an individual with a complete understanding of individual emotions, norms, and the interpersonal challenges faced by them. The significant correlation, which was found in the study, supports models such as Bishop et al (2004) Two Component Model.

In the component model, there are only two components which are Decisional Forgiveness and Emotional Forgiveness. Decision Forgiveness is which intentional decision to forgive those who have broken a particular rule or the one who has hurt an individual, then this component has been used to decide or a step to forget the trauma or the pain from an individual's life. The second one is Emotional Forgiveness, which by its name says that the emotion has been shifted from a negative emotion to a positive emotion, such as from aggression to empathy or self-compassion (Worthington & Scherer, 2004).

Similarly, in the model of forgiveness, there is another Model named the Enright Process (1991) in which the individual identifies the anger, takes the decision to forgive and transforms their emotional state of mind from negative emotion to positive emotion, which helps the individual to increase the level of mindfulness and forgiveness (Witvliet et al., 2001). In mental health, practicing

mindfulness-based intervention (MBI) helps an individual overcome their problems, give suggestions to their problems and resolve resentment or any kind of conflict or difference among individuals. Programmes such as Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) and Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) help people to practice self-compassion and not engage in painful experiences (Shapiro et al., 2006; Carson et al., 2005).

There was no such gender difference, but in future, if the sample size is large and more diverse, then there might be some kind of significant difference (Allemand et al., 2012). So, in the end, from all the findings, we can say that the individual with a higher level of mindfulness are generally associated with greater forgiveness. In middle adulthood, people using mindfulness properly have been seen enhancing their well-being and interpersonal relationships (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Thompson et al., 2005).

Implications of the Study

The findings of the present study imply several theoretical and practical implications. First, the observed positive relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness affirms the importance of cultivating mindfulness as an avenue to promote emotional regulation, empathy, and embrace key elements that facilitate forgiveness. This perception contributes to the growing body of research within positive psychology, suggesting that mindfulness-based practices can serve as effective tools for enhancing psychological well-being and interpersonal harmony among middle-aged adults. Second, the absence of significant gender differences implies that interventions aimed at facilitating mindfulness and forgiveness can be equally beneficial for both men and women, allowing for more integrative program designs. Third, these results have practical relevance for counselors, therapists, and mental health practitioners, who can embed mindfulness training into therapeutic frameworks to assist clients in managing resentment, conflict, and emotional distress. Lastly, at a societal level, promoting mindfulness and forgiveness education may strengthen improved relational dynamics, resilience, and overall life satisfaction in midlife populations.

Conclusion

The present study explored the relationship between mindfulness and forgiveness among middle-aged adults with an emphasis on potential gender differences. The findings revealed a moderately significant positive correlation between mindfulness and forgiveness, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of mindfulness are more likely to demonstrate greater forgiveness, psychological well-being, and healthier interpersonal relationships. Gender-based analysis indicated minimal variation, showing no significant difference between males and females in their levels of mindfulness and forgiveness, which implies that both genders possess similar capacities for emotional regulation, self-compassion, and empathy. Overall, the study highlights the beneficial influence of mindfulness in enhancing forgiveness, promoting emotional balance, resolving interpersonal conflicts, and fostering self-kindness and understanding. These results emphasize the importance of mindfulness-based practices as effective strategies for improving psychological well-being and maintaining relational harmony during middle adulthood.

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